

Tracking sources of biased decision-making in medical language models: a case study on gender bias

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Abstract

Though recent advances in medical large language models (LLMs) indicate the great potential of language models (LMs) in healthcare, other studies showed these AI doctors were biased as human doctors did. The current study tracked three sources of bias in LMs: bias in LMs, bias in clinical data, and the interaction between the former two. Through word embedding, we found that, compared to BERT base, Bio+Clinical BERT was gender-biased for certain symptoms, indicating potential bias in its training data. We further examined how biases affected the decision-making of LMs in a downstream task of gender prediction. Leveraging two masking strategies, we found that models were affected not only by biases in model and training data but also by an interaction between the two. Altogether, our results captured how different sources of bias affected the decision-making in language models, informing further understanding on the underlying mechanisms of biased medical LMs.

Background

Recently, large language models (LLMs) showed comparable performance as human doctors (Goh et al., 2025; Tu et al., 2024), indicating potential application of AI doctors in healthcare. On the other hand, AI doctors seemed to be as biased as human—LLMs make medical decisions with biases in socioeconomic status, age, gender, and ethnicity (Omar et al., 2025), the exact same biases existing in healthcare (Caballo et al., 2021; Ganguli et al., 2024; Hall et al., 2015;

Westergaard et al., 2019). Therefore, the industry and the society need to be cautious that the application of LLMs shall not accelerate healthcare inequality. Nevertheless, for efficient and effective prevention or remedies, we first need to understand and target the sources of bias. There are three potential sources: bias in language models (LMs) like LLMs, (Bolukbasi et al., 2016; Caliskan et al., 2017; Echterhoff et al., 2024), bias in clinical data (FitzGerald & Hurst, 2017; Hall et al., 2015), and the interaction between the two.

The current study first demonstrated biased behavior of a common LLM through role-play prompting. Then, we targeted sources of bias in order to help understand the mechanisms underlying gender-biased medical decision-making in LMs. First, for bias in LMs, we examined gender biases in word embeddings of two pre-trained BERTs. One was domain-general BERT base (Devlin et al., 2019), which has been found gender biased (Delobelle et al., 2022). The other one was domain-specific Bio+Clinical BERT (Alsentzer et al., 2019). Secondly, for bias in clinical data, we used a data set of patient notes. As a part of electronic health records (EHR), patient notes are often biased but are used to train clinical LLMs (Tang et al., 2024). Since Bio+Clinical BERT is fine-tuned on clinical text, it also captures potential biases from clinical data. Lastly, for an interaction between bias in LMs and that in clinical data, we further trained the models to perform a downstream task of gender prediction. We designed two masking strategies to reveal how gender biases from different sources would interact and bias decision-making of models.

Methods

Datasets and preprocessing

We used patient notes in Clinical Skills examination when test-takers interacted with standardized patients during the United States Medical Licensing Examination® (USMLE®). The datasets were accessed through the “Score Clinical Patient Notes” Kaggle challenge,¹ including 42,126 patient notes on 10 distinct patient cases. Data were text normalized, grouped, and chunked for training.

Manifesting Biases in common LLMs through Prompting

We used prompts and role-playing to test gender biases in LLMs under medical context. The prompt (see Appendix A) was adapted from previous research (Robinson et al., 2024). We interacted locally with Llama 3.1-8b through Ollama. After Llama was ready to answer questions about a patient, we further prompted it to guess whether the patient was male or female.

Word Embedding and Bias Evaluation

Through word embedding, we targeted bias in models. Specifically, we measured gender bias in word embeddings of medical symptoms in two pre-trained BERTs, domain-general BERT base and domain-specific Bio+Clinical BERT. In addition, the difference between the models would reflect potential biases in clinical data that were used to train Bio+Clinical BERT.

Through a downstream task of gender prediction, we targeted bias in clinical data and that in the interaction between biases in model and data. Specifically, we assessed how biases in data (training data for pre-trained BERTs and that for downstream task) biased decision-making of models. We hypothesized that medical symptoms, like occupations, are gender biased. The bias can transfer to model behavior. We systematically masked gender and symptoms in four

¹ <https://www.kaggle.com/c/nbme-score-clinical-patient-notes/overview>

experiments to test how different biases independently and interactively affected model predictions. In experiment 1 and 2 (gender+symptom masked), we masked 17 gender-related and 94 symptoms (Zhou et al., 2021) terms during training. In experiment 3 and 4 (gender masked), we only masked gender terms. Experiment 1 and 3 were trained on BERT base. Experiment 2 and 4 were trained on Bio+Clinical BERT. Training parameters were batch size = 6, learning rate = $2e-5$, and optimizer = AdamW. We used cross entropy loss and perplexity for evaluation, aligning with standard evaluation metrics. Validation used 6,748 notes from Cases 6 and 9 (one male, one female, both annotated with 'fever'). Gender bias was tested on Case 0 (2218 notes) and 7 (4046 notes). The remaining 31,297 notes used for model training (five female cases and one male case).

Post-training, models predicted the gender of masked tokens in all patient notes of Case 0 and 7. Gender prediction of each note was quantified by prediction distribution at token level. If most tokens in a note were predicted as male, gender prediction of this note was “male.” Same for female prediction. If tokens had equal number for both gender terms, the gender prediction was labeled as “mixed.”

Results

LLM possesses common stereotypes

Through prompting and role-play, there was an indicated over-representation of “western, educated, industrialized, rich, and democratic” populations in training data of Llama. That is, Llama assumed people with access to medical resources were more likely to be middle-class, in line with previously found biases in LLMs.

In addition, gender bias existed in framing. That is, language uses like “SYMPTOM is more associated with male/female.” When we showed Llama two notes from the same patient (both mentioned “sharp” chest pain), it gave different assumptions on the population distribution of chest pain and myocarditis but gave the exact same reasoning (see Appendix A). Here, we recall that many bias benchmarks use multiple-choice questions with an unbiased option. Nevertheless, models passing bias benchmarks were still implicitly biased (Bai et al., 2025) and LLMs were biased when producing content (Hu et al., 2024). The patterns here emphasized the way using LLMs could lead to implicit biases—another potential source of biases.

Bias in datasets and in models

To target biases in language models, we quantified gender bias in word embeddings of symptom terms in a BERT base and Bio+Clinical BERT. Based on cosine similarity between gender and symptoms terms, Bio+Clinical BERT was biased towards female (symptoms closer to female terms than to male terms, $t(1548) = 4.35, p < 0.0001$). BERT base, though not showing gender bias on our symptom list ($p = 0.873$), some symptoms seemed to be biased through multidimensional scaling. For example, “weight loss” was closer to “female.”

To target biases in clinical data and their interaction with biases in models, we trained the BERT models with another data set of patient notes. In four experiments, we trained models in a downstream task of gender prediction to test how gender biases from different sources biased the decision-making of models (see Appendix B for model training and evaluation). For Case 7 (female), models in all experiments made correct prediction on most notes, with BERT base (Exp 1 and 3) making more correct prediction under both masking strategies (**Figure 1B**). However, for Case 0 (male), only Bio+Clinical BERT with gender and symptom masked (Exp 3)

led to correct prediction on most notes (**Figure 1A**). When only gender was masked, both BERTs rarely made correct prediction. Bias in our training data could lead to this low accuracy, since there were more female cases. Moreover, Bio+Clinical BERT (Exp 4) made less correct prediction, in other words, more female guesses. This bias towards female was in line with the gender bias found in word embeddings of symptoms in Bio-Clinical BERT. When only gender was masked, symptoms, that were gender biased, could have driven biased decision-making, reflecting an interaction of different sources of bias.

Figure 1. Model prediction on gender in four experiments for Case 0 and 7.

A. Gender prediction on all notes of Case 0 (male) in four experiments. Distribution of predicted gender for all notes are correspondingly marked as blue, orange, and green for male, female, and mixed prediction. The number of correct prediction is marked within corresponding ground-truth gender category.

B. Gender prediction on all notes of Case 7 (female) in four experiments. Same convention as A.

Discussion

In this study, we first demonstrated implicit biases in LLMs in generating responses, emphasizing cautious interaction with LLMs to avoid bias. Then, to target sources of bias in biased behavior of LMs, we measured gender bias in word embeddings and that in decision-making in a downstream task of gender prediction. We found that, Bio+Clinical BERT was more gender biased in certain clinical symptoms than BERT base. This indicated potential gender bias in clinical text used to train Bio+Clinical BERT. Such bias led to bias in model and potentially

drove biased decision-making in models, as Bio+Clinical BERT was biased towards female in the downstream task when only gender was masked.

On the other hand, when trained with biased data in a task, BERT base seemed to be more gender biased than Bio-Clinical BERT. When both gender and symptoms were masked, only Bio-Clinical BERT made correct prediction on Case 0, while BERT base made biased prediction towards female. In addition, when all models were correct, BERT base made more female prediction. These patterns cannot be explained by current results and further analyses are needed. Yet, the results highlight that the interaction between bias in model and bias in data complicated biased decision-making in models.

In conclusion, instead of large-scale bias evaluation, the current study examined details in biased decision-making in models to target sources of bias. Our results provided potential explanation for mechanisms underlying some biased behavior in models.

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